

Intelligent System Architectures

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Abstract. Systems of Systems (SoS) have started to emerge as a consequence of the general trend toward the integration of beforehand isolated systems. To unleash the full potential, the contained systems must be able to operate as elements in open, dynamic, and deviating SoS architectures and to adapt to open and dynamic contexts while being developed, operated, evolved, and governed independently. We name the resulting advanced SoS to be *smart* as they must be self-adaptive at the level of the individual systems and self-organizing at the SoS level to cope with the emergent behavior at that level. In this paper we analyze the open challenges for the envisioned smart SoS. In addition, we discuss our ideas for tackling this vision with our SMARTSOS approach that employs open and adaptive collaborations and models at runtime. In particular, we focus on preliminary ideas for the construction and assurance of smart SoS.

1 Introduction

Systems of Systems (SoS) [1,2] nowadays become a highly relevant challenge as the general trend can be observed that beforehand isolated systems are integrated into larger federations of systems. To unleash the full potential of such federations, SoS must be *smart* such that the contained systems are able to operate as elements in open, dynamic, and deviating SoS architectures and to adapt to open and dynamic contexts while being developed, operated, evolved, and governed independently.¹ Therefore, the resulting smart SoS must be selfadaptive at the level of the individual systems and self-organizing at the SoS level to cope with the emergent behavior at that level.

For a smart SoS holds that each of its systems has to be *independent* in the sense that it is developed, operated, evolved, and governed independently from

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¹ Similar needs are observed for specific cases of SoS, such as *ultra-large-scale systems* [3] focusing on issues arising from the complexity of SoS or *cyber-physical systems* [4] emphasizing the integration of the physical and cyber world.

the other systems in the SoS. Furthermore, these systems interact with each other in an open and dynamic world (cf. [5]), which causes individual systems to dynamically join or leave the SoS over time, the SoS architecture to deviate, and emergent behavior at the *SoS level*.

Moreover, each independent system must adapt its behavior autonomously according to its own needs and peer systems in the SoS (*self-adaptation* [6, 7]) while considering the interplay between its own behavior, the other systems' behavior, and the required SoS-level behavior (*self-organization* [8]). The envisioned interaction between the systems involves independently developed systems and requires means for exchanging knowledge between these systems at runtime. This knowledge covers aspects of a running system itself and the context or the requirements of a running system. While the outlined rich interaction is key, the development of the systems has to scale and thus only can take into account the publically available knowledge about possible collaborations with the other systems. Finally, the systems as part of a smart SoS will evolve in order to adjust to new needs or changing regulations (cf. *software evolution* [9]). Since it seems today improbable or even impossible that all the required evolution steps can be covered automatically by a system itself (e.g., by self-adaptation or self-organization), it must still be possible that required evolution steps for each individually governed system are performed during the operation of the SoS. These challenges for engineering smart SoS are currently hardly covered by the available approaches.

The current state of the art suggests constructing SoS using an architecture perspective and services (cf. [10]) employing, for example, the *Service oriented architecture Modeling Language (SoaML)* [11] and the *Unified Modeling Language (UML)* [12] to specify the cooperation of systems by means of service contracts and collaborations. In these collaborations, roles with dedicated interfaces describe the behavior of the systems while the SoS-level behavior emerges from the interactions of these roles.

The use of collaborations for the modeling of services [13,14], the use of class diagrams for the structure and graph transformations for the behavior modeling [15,16], and a formal model of ensembles [17] have been proposed. However, none of these approaches supports the construction of dynamic collaborations as required for smart SoS where systems dynamically join or leave the federation. And even though well-established formal approaches such as π -calculus [18] or bigrahs [19] tackle such structural dynamics, to the best of our knowledge no work exists that especially covers the problem of providing assurances for dynamic collaborations of arbitrary size. Either the approaches require an initial system configuration and only support finite state systems (or systems for which an abstract finite state model of moderate size exist) [15,20–24] or they lack the expressive power to describe typical problems concerning the structural dynamics [25,26].

In our own Mechatronic UML approach (mUML) [27] for the modeldriven development of self-optimizing embedded real-time systems, we already support collaborations of self-optimizing autonomous systems in a rigorous manner by means of role protocols. For mUML and its collaboration concepts an overall assurance scheme has been presented in [28]: it combines a modular verification approach [29] for the component hierarchies of the autonomous systems, the compositional verification [30] of ad hoc real-time collaborations between the autonomous systems, and a fully automatic checker for inductive invariants of graph transformation system rules [31] describing the possible changes of the dynamic architecture at the SoS level. Additional work on assurances for mUML employs a multi-agent system view on an SoS to study how commitments between the collaborating systems can be modeled and

analyzed [32]. Therefore, with mUML an approach exists that provides assurances for systems that combine self-adaptive autonomous systems similar to an SoS. However, in contrast to the challenges of smart SoS, which are discussed in the next section, mUML provides no solution for collaborations with structural dynamics of the roles, is restricted to homogeneous systems (i.e., systems that evolve jointly and similarly and that have complete knowledge about each other), and does not support the runtime exchange of complex knowledge. Moreover, the self-adaptation is limited to pre-planned reconfigurations in hierarchical architectures.

Our Executable Runtime Megamodels approach (EUREMA) [33] for the model-driven engineering of self-adaptive systems supports – in contrast to mUML – the flexible specification of self-adaptation by allowing us to employ abstract runtime models (cf. [34]) of the context and the system itself such that the self-adaptation behavior can be specified by rules operating on such abstractions. However, EUREMA is so far limited to centralized and non-distributed systems and does not address collaborations or the self-organizing SoS level.

In this paper, we will first analyze open challenges for engineering smart SoS. We will then discuss our *Software with Models at Runtime for Systems of Systems* (SMARTSOS) vision that employs collaborations and generic models at runtime for trustworthy self-organization and evolution of the systems at the SoS level and self-adaptation within the systems while taking the independent development, operation, management, and evolution of these systems into account. We will particularly outline the formal foundations underlying SMARTSOS based on graph transformation systems [35,36] which cover in principle the identified challenges for the construction and assurance of smart SoS.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, we discuss open challenges for smart SoS. Afterwards, our SMARTSOS vision is outlined in Section 3. Then, the concepts for constructing smart SoS with collaborations, components, and runtime models are outlined in Section 4. Afterwards, the results that enable the assurance for the smart SoS are presented in Section 5. The paper closes with a discussion of these results in Section 6 and provides in Section 7 some concluding remarks and an outlook on future work.

2 Challenges

SoS as a composition of systems that are operationally and managerially independent from each other [1] is characterized by uncoordinated evolution steps and geographic distribution of these systems (cf. [37]). Additionally, dynamic

Table 1. Summary of the Identified Challenges.

Construction/Assurance of Self-Adaptation (C1/A1)
Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Interactions for Self-Organization (C2/A2)
Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Structural Dynamics (C3/A3)
Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Runtime Knowledge Exchange (C4/A4)
Construction/Assurance of Evolution of Smart SoS (C5/A5)
Scalable Construction/Assurance of Smart SoS (C6/A6)
Construction/Assurance of Smart SoS with Restricted Knowledge (C7/A7)

configuration capabilities, resilience, the ability to dynamically adapt and absorb deviations in the SoS structure, and the ability to deal with emergent behavior in context of self-organization that goes beyond developing contractual descriptions are crucial [2]

for smart SoS. These issues are challenging since each system as part of a smart SoS is *independent* in the sense that it is developed, operated, evolved, and governed independently from the other systems in the same SoS. Furthermore, the systems interact with each other in an open and dynamic world (cf. [5]), which causes individual systems to dynamically join or leave the smart SoS over time, the SoS architecture to deviate, and emergent behavior at the *SoS level*. Consequently, the SoS-level architecture and behavior are not controlled by a single, centralized authority.

As example in this paper we consider a large-scale transport system where different organizations operate fleets of autonomously driving shuttles that share a track system. This constitutes an SoS since the shuttles are operated, managed, and evolved by different authorities, they dynamically interact with each other (e.g., to build convoys), and they adapt to their own and the other shuttle's states and behavior (e.g., to decrease the speed when the shuttle's own battery level is low or when the speed of the shuttle running ahead decreases).¹

Engineering such smart SoS imposes several challenges that we outline in Table 1. All of them aim for means for the construction and assurance of smart SoS and its individual systems, which must take the operational and managerial independence of the individual systems and the emergent behavior at the SoS level into account.

The first challenge considers the *Construction/Assurance of Self-Adaptation (C1/A1)* of the individual systems as each system within a smart SoS must adapt its behavior according to its own needs and the behavior of other systems as well as the emergent SoS-level behavior (cf. [38,39]). For instance, a shuttle adapts its speed to its battery level, to the speed of the shuttle running ahead, or to an agreement established by all shuttles in a convoy. Such changes of the behavior must be systematically constructed and assured to enable trustworthy operation and in particular self-adaptation [6,7].

Due to the operational and managerial independence of the systems, the *Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Interactions for Self-Organization (C2/A2)* challenge captures that the interactions among these systems must be selforganizing (cf. [8]) to achieve the SoS-level goals. For example, shuttles from different organization must interact to avoid collisions or they may even cooperate to build convoys in order to save energy. Such interplays of autonomous shuttles must be systematically constructed and assured to provide confidence for satisfying SoS-level goals (e.g., reliable and safe rail traffic).

Furthermore, since the operational context changes or the systems dynamically join or leave the SoS such that the SoS-level architecture dynamically changes, the challenge of the *Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Structural Dynamics (C3/A3)* must be supported. For instance, autonomous shuttles may join or leave a convoy and the other shuttles already part of the convoy must account for it. Such dynamics must be constructed and assured to guarantee certain SoS-level behavior resulting from the interactions.

Additionally to the structural dynamics, the *Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Runtime Knowledge Exchange (C4/A4)* is required since no system in the SoS typically has *all* the knowledge needed to achieve the SoS-level goals at runtime. This calls for

¹ See <http://www.railcab.de> for an example with the outlined characteristics.

exchanging knowledge between interacting systems. This knowledge refers to the current state, context, and requirements of individual systems. For instance, shuttles establishing a convoy may exchange their driving modes to agree on a common mode for the whole convoy. Such a knowledge exchange must be constructed and assured when engineering interactions to gain confidence that the SoS-level goals can be achieved.

In parallel to the self-adaptive and self-organizing behavior of systems in the SoS, the systems evolve in an uncoordinated way as they are managed independently from each other by different organizations. Evolution is caused by the permanent need to change the software in response to changing requirements of the stakeholders, no longer valid assumptions, or changing regulations the software has to adhere to (cf. *software evolution* [9]). With evolution, we refer to introducing new or removing existing types of systems or interactions (and therefore, also behavior) from the SoS. For example, new shuttle versions that support new cooperation mechanisms are integrated into the SoS and they must not interfere with the already existing versions. To handle such radical changes in a trustworthy manner and to support the long-term existence of the SoS, the *Construction/Assurance of Evolution of Smart SoS (C5/A5)* is a main challenge.

In general, engineering smart SoS is challenging due to the ultra-large scale and complexity of such systems and due to the different authorities managing such systems. Therefore, the *Scalable Construction/Assurance of Smart SoS (C6/A6)* and the *Construction/Assurance of Smart SoS with Restricted Knowledge (C7/A7)* are also important aspects for the engineering. The first aspect is motivated by the fact that it is not feasible to construct the whole SoS upfront before its deployment, or to analyze *all* possible SoS configurations or architectures that grow exponentially with the number of participating systems. For instance, any number of shuttles of arbitrary types may run on the track system or may cooperate in a convoy. Thus, the construction and assurances for SoS must scale with the size of the SoS. The second aspect refers to the construction and assurances for smart SoS, which must work despite the restricted knowledge that participants of the SoS have. An organization responsible for an individual system in the SoS or the system itself might have no global view of the SoS and no concrete information about the other participants and possible interactions among participants. Nevertheless, assurances for each system and the SoS must be provided to enable trustworthy operations. For example, when constructing and assuring new shuttle versions supporting a certain interaction, details about other organizations' shuttle versions that are potential cooperators for the interaction might not be available. However, the construction and assurance must cope with the limited knowledge available.

These open challenges, each with a construction and assurance dimension as summarized in Table 1, reveal the difficulty of engineering and ruling smart SoS due to the complexity, dynamics, emergence, and decentralized management and governance.

3 SMARTSOS

In our vision SMARTSOS, we suggest combining the benefits of mUML and EUREMA to tackle the challenges for smart SoS. However, we do not suggest simply integrating

the ideas of both approaches. Instead we developed a radically different and more abstract perspective on the SoS-level interactions to overcome the limitations of the state-of-the-art and former approaches and to master the complexity of smart SoS. This novel perspective is based on the combination of runtime models and collaborations.

3.1 Runtime Models

To realize the challenge of the Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Runtime Knowledge Exchange (C4/A4), SMARTSOS employs *models at runtime* [34] that suggest following model-driven engineering principles to engineer abstract runtime representations of running systems or their contexts and requirements. Such models are said to be *causally connected* to the running system, which means that changes in the system are reflected in the model and vice versa. Thus, “change agents (e.g., software maintainers, software-based agents) use [abstract] runtime models to modify executing software in a controlled manner” [40, p.39] rather than directly adapting the running software at the code level.

With EUREMA we have extended this perspective by providing runtime models at different levels of abstraction [41] and by specifying the adaptation itself, that is, software-based agents, using runtime models [33]. The latter aspect leverages the flexibility of runtime models for managing the change agents at runtime in addition to the running systems. In SMARTSOS, we go another step further and suggest using *generic* in contrast to highly specific and optimized runtime models, which eases interoperability and evolution of systems in an SoS, as it excludes individual optimization and specific solution for the runtime models.

For an individual system in a smart SoS, such generic runtime models may capture the system’s state, context, requirements, and adaptation logic. These models may be used locally for self-adaptation and assurances that each system fulfills its requirements. As discussed in the following, they may also be used for

Fig.1. Local and shared runtime models of a complex SoS architecture.

collaborations among systems leading to the self-organization of the SoS, which requires the exchange of runtime knowledge.

The basic idea to integrate runtime models and collaborations for the construction of smart SoS is depicted in Fig. 1. At first, each running system living in the cyber world may have a view on its physical context and its own state in the cyber and physical world by means of runtime models of the *context* and the *self*. In general, we consider runtime descriptions reflecting the running system and its context as *Reflection Models*. Particularly, *System Models* (Self in Fig. 1) reflect about architectural and behavioral key aspects of the system and they are causally connected to the system. *Context Models* (Context in Fig. 1) describe the environmental situation of a system (cf. [42,43]). In our example, models of the Context and Self are depicted in the individual Shuttle systems in Fig. 1. This supports designing the self-adaptation of the shuttles as MAPEK feedback loops (**M**onitor/**A**nalyze/**P**lan/**E**xecute-**K**nowledge) [44] while the knowledge part is implemented by the runtime models. Such feedback loops are realized by analyze and plan activities that operate on the basis of the runtime models while linking the runtime models to the system and context is realized by the monitor and execute activities. The Self and Context runtime models can refer to the local state of a shuttle (e.g., the Mode and Battery status) as well as the available information about the context (e.g., whether there is another shuttle driving on the tracks ahead of the shuttle). This context does not only consist of the physical context such as the shuttle's position, the topology of the track system, and the positions of other shuttles nearby, but additionally the

Fig.2. Visibility of local and shared runtime models.

context in the cyber world. This cyber-world context covers, for instance, the established collaboration instances and context shared with other roles of these collaboration instances.

As depicted in Fig. 1, these runtime models of the context and self constitute an overall local runtime model, that is, the Reflection Model, for each `:Shuttle` system. As described in Fig. 2 in more detail, each system does not only operate on information

about its own local context and itself, but can also get access to the information stored in runtime models of other systems concerning their context or themselves.² In our example, the left most Shuttle system has also access to information in form of runtime models in quite different ways. The directly visible elements are the information available local to the shuttle by means of runtime models (white with solid frame). Additional information like the position of the shuttle in front of it, which is encoded by the on edge between that shuttle and its current track, is accessible for shuttles that knows the Coord collaboration type (gray with dashed frame). Finally, information about the mode of the shuttle system in front of it is accessible for a shuttle, if it is connected to this via a Coord collaboration instance (gray with solid frame).

Likewise to EUREMA, the behavior of the systems in reaction to particular situations can now be directly described based on such overall local runtime models. This is illustrated at the top of the left-hand side of Fig. 2 showing the feedback loop (i.e., the monitor, analyze, plan, and execute activities) of a shuttle realizing the self-adaptation and therefore, addressing the Construction of Self-Adaptation (C1) challenge. In the following, we will elaborate the use of such generic runtime models in the context of collaborations. In general, such models as employed by SMARTSOS provide an idealization of the systems and contexts, which is discussed in Section 4.3.

3.2 Collaborations

To approach the challenges of the Construction/Assurance of SoS-Level Interactions for Self-Organization (C2/A2) and the Construction/Assurance of SoS Level Structural Dynamics (C3/A3) while taking aspects of the Scalable Construction/Assurance of Smart SoS (C6/A6) and the Construction/Assurance of Smart SoS with Restricted Knowledge (C7/A7) into account, *SoaML* and *UML* provide basic concepts of modeling collaborations. They support specifying abstract collaboration types and corresponding roles. The interaction of roles is defined by sequence or activity diagrams and *UML* interface descriptions (in form of class diagrams). Role behavior may be also covered by protocol state machines. The mUML approach goes beyond the ideas of *SoaML* and *UML* by describing the possible interaction always via real-time variant of state machines for each role and the communication medium. Due to the well-defined semantics for all employed formalism such as the real-time variant of state machines, mUML enables the basic verification of the interactions through model checking.

SMARTSOS supports a more flexible concept for collaborations compared to mUML and *SoaML/UML*. In SMARTSOS a richer language to specify the collaborations is provided, which also covers the exchange of complex information as well as specifying structural dynamics covering, for example, how systems can join the collaboration, leave the collaboration, or how the structure of the collaboration may change at runtime. In order to ensure interoperability and achieve trustworthy behavior at the SoS level, we furthermore need also more sophisticated analysis capabilities, for

² In the case of heterogeneous local runtime models, efficient incremental model synchronization techniques such as triple graph grammars [45] can be employed. Such techniques realize required translation steps between runtime models that are specified in different modeling languages but that capture similar content. We already applied them to create and maintain multiple runtime models of a system in [41].

example, to investigate the impact from one system part to another through collaborations.

The basic idea of separating the required interactions into separated collaborations is depicted in Fig. 1. The autonomous systems of the SoS can connect with each other as specified by the collaboration types and can establish collaboration instances to cooperate as needed. For example, the two left most Shuttle instances in Fig. 1 are linked by a Coord collaboration instance to build a temporary convoy and the right most Shuttle instance is linked to a Station instance by an Allocate collaboration instance.

It has to be noted that different collaboration types and their involved views on the physical or cyber world may not be disjoint. In such a case, the construction and assurance for the collaboration types that share some of their elements of the physical or cyber world have to take such overlapping into account. The required concepts for abstract shared collaborations types that includes runtime models with overlapping entities are discussed in Section 4.3.

The elements of the Coord collaboration type are defined in the class diagram depicted on the left hand side of Fig. 3. The Coord collaboration element as well as the Shuttle role with its Mode and Battery status are introduced using the stereotypes *collab* for collaborations and *role* for roles. The class diagram also defines the track topology, that is, multiple Track elements connected

Fig.3. Class diagram of the collaboration type Coord (left); properties of the collaboration type Coord as forbidden SPs (middle and right).

with each other by the next relationship, as well as the positioning of the Shuttles on the tracks by the on relationship.

The class diagram of a collaboration type implicitly specifies in form of all valid object configurations for the class diagram the possible states the collaboration may be in. Later on, we define rules that refer to such object configurations to capture the system behavior. We formally define these object configurations as attributed graphs in Section 4.

create shuttle

move

Fig.4. Behavior rules for the Shuttle role of the Coord collaboration as SPs.

To capture the laws that should hold for the different collaboration types, we specify *behavior rules* with Story Patterns (SPs) [45] that define the permitted and mandatory behavior of each role, *read rules* with SPs having no side effects that define the visibility of shared runtime models, and the *properties* the collaboration has to ensure. These properties are described by SPs without side effects in the case of simple state properties and with Timed Story Sequence Diagrams (TSSDs) [46] in the case of sequence properties. A major duty for the SoS-level assurance is to ensure that the properties are the guaranteed outcome of the roles' behavior.

Fig. 4 depicts the *behavior rules*, that is, the SPs defining the permitted and mandatory behavior of each role of the Coord collaboration (we refer to [47] for the complete set of behavior rules). The SP called *move in coordination* on the lower right-hand side of Fig. 4, for example, describes that after the building of a platoon encoded by the existence of the Coord instance, the rear shuttle instance can move with a reduced distance behind the front shuttle instance and therefore, both shuttle instances may even be positioned on the same Track instance. The instance name *self* used in a rule determines the role of the collaboration, for which this rule is intended, in this example, for the shuttle role (cf. *self:Shuttle* element). Furthermore, the *create coordination* SP defines that shuttles must create a collaboration if they are on neighboring tracks and do not yet collaborate (i.e., there is no Coord instance yet).

A simple SP denotes two graphs at once. The first one is the left-hand-side graph L that you try to find in the current instance situation encoded in the graph G and that consists of all unmarked elements and those marked with *destroy*. The second one is right-hand-side graph R that consists of all unmarked elements and those marked with *create*. If L can be matched in G , the SP rule can be applied. A rule application on G results in the replacement of the match of L in G by R . In the case of complex SPs that have a negative application condition (NAC) that defines a graph L^0 resulting from extending L by all the crossed-out elements. Then, besides finding the left-hand-side graph L in G there must exist *no* match for the NAC L^0 in G that extends that match for L . Otherwise, the rule cannot be applied.

On the upper right-hand side of Fig. 4, the *move* SP specifies using such a NAC that shuttles can move forward along the track over time if there is no other shuttle on the next track. Additionally, the SP defines a temporal condition that a shuttle must stay on

a track at least ten time units before it can move to the next track. This temporal condition ensures that the move SP can only be applied with respect to realistic physical movement conditions of the shuttles. If the shuttle moves, the on reference is created on the t2 Track and the clock attribute timeAtTrack of the shuttle is reseted to zero. As a consequence, the shuttle has to stay on the next track again at least for ten time units before the move SP can be applied again.

Fig. 5 shows an example of an application of a graph transformation rule. If we consider the instance situation (start graph) on the left-hand side and apply the move SP rule from Figure 4, first a match for the move SP has to be found. Thereby, we can find a match, where the shuttle instance *self* from Figure 4 is

Fig.5. Application of the move SP from Figure 4 on an exemplary instance situation. matched to the *s1* shuttle instance on the left side in Figure 5. Because there is no other shuttle on the next track t2, the move SP can be applied for the found match with the consequence that the on link from shuttle s1 to track t1 is deleted and a new on link from shuttle s1 to track t2 is created. Thus, we obtain the instance situation (result graph) as depicted on the right-hand side on Figure 5.

The *properties* the collaboration type Coord should guarantee are depicted in Fig. 3. We have the forbidden situations collision and missing collaboration that must not happen. Hence, these properties are marked with $\neg\exists$. For example, the collision SP in the middle of Fig. 3 shows the situation where two shuttles that are not collaborating with each other are on the same track, that is, these two shuttles may collide. Furthermore, the missing collaboration SP on the right-hand side of Fig. 3 reflects the faulty situation where two shuttles are on neighboring tracks but they do not collaborate with each other. Both situations have to be excluded to ensure a proper operation of the collaboration. For both instance situations in Figure 5 must hold that all specified properties are fulfilled (that the forbidden collision and missing collaboration SP cannot be matched).

Fig.6. Read rules for the Shuttle role of the Coord collaboration type as SPs.

The *read rules* for the collaboration type Coord are depicted in Fig. 6 using SPs and so called *path expressions* that allow us to describe the fraction of the runtime models

that can be accessed in a more compact form than standard SPs without such path expressions. In general, read rules on the one hand describe what the roles can access (read) but also imply on the other hand that the other roles somehow have to provide the related information. In any case, the self instance name in a read rule that must always be present determines for which role this rule specifies access to other runtime models. The optional provider instance name if present in a rule indicates whether a related role is in charge of providing that information.

The first read rule, called *common*, describes that it is assumed that a shuttle (marked with the self instance name) has access to the complete track topology because the path expression `next[0..*]` denotes any finite path between two Tracks with arbitrary many omitted and thus not visible nodes in between. Looking at the class diagram in Fig. 3, it reveals that the omitted nodes must always be of type *Track* and thus, the path expression represents all sequences of Tracks connected by *next* edges. As this read rule does not require any instance of the *Coord* collaboration, it denotes that each shuttle knows the track topology on its own (a possible implementation would be that each shuttle has a map of the track topology).

The read rule *detect-obstacle* for the *Shuttle* role (cf. self instance name) employs the path expression `next[0..3]` to denote a path between two Tracks with 0 to 3 not visible Tracks in between. The provider instance name for the other *Shuttle* role indicates that this role must provide this fragments of its runtime model. As this read rule does not require any instance of the *Coord* collaboration, it defines that the shuttles are able to see other shuttles nearby even though no collaboration has been established yet (a possible implementation can be based on GPS and a related protocol to broadcast position data to the shuttle's vicinity [48]). The read rule *share-mode* for the *Shuttle* role (cf. self instance name) is different as it always requires an instance of the *Coord* collaboration. Otherwise, it does not allow a shuttle to retrieve (read) the mode of the other *Shuttle* role. The provider instance name for that *Shuttle* role indicates that this role must provide this data.

4 Construction

To cover in particular the challenges of the Construction of SoS-Level Interactions for Self-Organization (C2), Construction of SoS-Level Structural Dynamics (C3), Construction of SoS-Level Runtime Knowledge Exchange (C4), Construction of Evolution of Smart SoS (C5), and Scalable Construction of Smart SoS (C6), SMARTSOS supports collaborations with a dynamic number of roles, runtime models, the independent evolution of the autonomous systems and their collaborations, and the specification of individual autonomous systems without having complete knowledge about the overall SoS. These aspects require at first a solid foundation for the concepts used for the construction and assurance of smart SoS. Based on this foundation we then can formally introduce types and instances of collaborations, systems, and SoS as well as the notions of runtime models and overlapping collaborations. Finally, we cover the evolution of smart SoS, that is, the set of types and instances of the SoS evolve (e.g., new types and instances are introduced).

References

1. Maier, M.W.: Architecting principles for systems-of-systems. *Systems Engineering* **1**(4) (1998) 267–284
2. Valerdi, R., Axelband, E., Baehren, T., Boehm, B., Dorenbos, D., Jackson, S., Madni, A., Nadler, G., Robitaille, P., Settles, S.: A research agenda for systems of systems architecting. *Intl. Journal of System of Systems Engineering* **1**(1-2) (2008) 171–188
3. Northrop, L., Feiler, P.H., Gabriel, R.P., Linger, R., Longstaff, T., Kazman, R., Klein, M., Schmidt, D.: *Ultra-Large-Scale Systems: The Software Challenge of the Future*. Software Engineering Institute, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA (2006)
4. Broy, M., Cengarle, M., Geisberger, E.: Cyber-Physical Systems: Imminent Challenges. In Calinescu, R., Garlan, D., eds.: *Large-Scale Complex IT Systems. Development, Operation and Management*. Volume 7539 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*. Springer (2012) 1–28
5. Baresi, L., Di Nitto, E., Ghezzi, C.: Toward Open-World Software: Issue and Challenges. *Computer* **39**(10) (2006) 36–43
6. Cheng, B.H., de Lemos, R., Giese, H., Inverardi, P., Magee, J., Andersson, J., Becker, B., Bencomo, N., Brun, Y., Cukic, B., Serugendo, G.D.M., Dustdar, S., Finkelstein, A., Gacek, C., Geihs, K., Grassi, V., Karsai, G., Kienle, H.M., Kramer, J., Litoiu, M., Malek, S., Mirandola, R., Müller, H., Park, S., Shaw, M., Tichy, M., Tivoli, M., Weyns, D., Whittle, J.: *Software Engineering for Self-Adaptive Systems: A Research Roadmap*. In Cheng, B.H., de Lemos, R., Giese, H., Inverardi, P., Magee, J., eds.: *Software Engineering for Self-Adaptive Systems*. Volume 5525 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*. Springer (2009) 1–26
7. de Lemos, R., Giese, H., Müller, H., Shaw, M., Andersson, J., Litoiu, M., Schmerl, B., Tamura, G., Villegas, N.M., Vogel, T., Weyns, D., Baresi, L., Becker, B., Bencomo, N., Brun, Y., Cukic, B., Desmarais, R., Dustdar, S., Engels, G., Geihs, K., Goeschka, K., Gorla, A., Grassi, V., Inverardi, P., Karsai, G., Kramer, J., Lopes, A., Magee, J., Malek, S., Mankovskii, S., Mirandola, R., Mylopoulos, J., Nierstrasz, O., Pezz'e, M., Prehofer, C., Schäfer, W., Schlichting, R., Smith, D.B., Sousa, J.P., Tahvildari, L., Wong, K., Wuttke, J.: *Software Engineering for Self-Adaptive Systems: A second Research Roadmap*. In de Lemos, R., Giese, H., Müller, H., Shaw, M., eds.: *Software Engineering for Self-Adaptive Systems II*. Volume 7475 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*. Springer (2013) 1–32
8. Di Marzo Serugendo, G., Gleizes, M.P., Karageorgos, A., eds.: *Self-organising Software*. *Natural Computing Series*. Springer (2011)
9. Mens, T., Demeyer, S.: *Software Evolution*. Springer (2008)
10. Mittal, S., Risco Martin, J.: Model-driven systems engineering for netcentric system of systems with DEVS unified process. In: *Simulation Conference (WSC), 2013 Winter*. (2013) 1140–1151
11. Object Management Group (OMG): *Service oriented architecture Modeling Language (SoaML) Specification, Version 1.0.1*. (2012)
12. : *UML 2.4 Superstructure Specification, Version 2.4*, ptc/2010-11-14 (2010)
13. Sanders, R.T., Castejo'n, H.N., Kraemer, F., Bræk, R.: Using UML 2.0 Collaborations for Compositional Service Specification. In: *Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems*. Volume 3713 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*, Springer (2005) 460–475
14. Broy, M., Krüger, I., Meisinger, M.: A formal model of services. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* **16**(1) (2007)

15. Baresi, L., Heckel, R., Thöne, S., Varró, D.: Modeling and Validation of ServiceOriented Architectures: Application vs. Style. In: Proceedings of the 9th European Software Engineering Conference Held Jointly with 11th ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering. ESEC/FSE-11, New York, NY, USA, ACM (2003) 68–77
16. Baresi, L., Heckel, R., Thöne, S., Varró, D.: Style-based modeling and refinement of service-oriented architectures. *Software and Systems Modeling* **5**(2) (2006) 187–207
17. Holz, M., Wirsing, M.: Towards a System Model for Ensembles. In Agha, G., Danvy, O., Meseguer, J., eds.: *Formal Modeling: Actors, Open Systems, Biological Systems*. Volume 7000 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*., Springer (2011) 241–261
18. Milner, R.: *Communicating and mobile systems: the π -calculus*. Cambridge University Press, New York, NY, USA (1999)
19. Milner, R.: *The Space and Motion of Communicating Agents*. Cambridge University Press (2009)
20. Varro, D.: Automated formal verification of visual modeling languages by model checking. *Software and System Modeling* **3**(2) (2004) 85–113
21. Rensink, A.: Towards model checking graph grammars. In: *Proc. of the 3rd Workshop on Automated Verification of Critical Systems, AVoCS, University of Southampton* (2003) 150–160
22. Frias, M.F., Galeotti, J.P., López Pombo, C.G., Aguirre, N.M.: DynAlloy: Upgrading Alloy with actions. In: *Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Software Engineering. ICSE '05, ACM* (2005) 442–451
23. Olveczky, P., Meseguer, J.: Specification and analysis of real-time systems using Real-Time Maude. In Wermelinger, M., Margaria-Steffen, T., eds.: *Fundamental Approaches to Software Engineering*. Volume 2984 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*., Springer (2004) 354–358
24. Zhang, J., Goldsby, H.J., Cheng, B.H.: Modular verification of dynamically adaptive systems. In: *Proceedings of the 8th ACM International Conference on Aspect-oriented Software Development. AOSD '09, New York, NY, USA, ACM* (2009) 161–172
25. Baldan, P., Corradini, A., König, B.: A static analysis technique for graph transformation systems. In Larsen, K., Nielsen, M., eds.: *CONCUR 2001 – Concurrency Theory*. Volume 2154 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*., Springer (2001) 381–395
26. Bauer, J., Wilhelm, R.: Static Analysis of Dynamic Communication Systems by Partner Abstraction. In Nielson, H., Filé, G., eds.: *Static Analysis*. Volume 4634 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*., Springer (2007) 249–264
27. Burmester, S., Giese, H., Münch, E., Oberschelp, O., Klein, F., Scheideler, P.: Tool Support for the Design of Self-Optimizing Mechatronic Multi-Agent Systems. *International Journal on Software Tools for Technology Transfer (STTT)* **10**(3) (2008) 207–222
28. Giese, H., Schäfer, W.: Model-Driven Development of Safe Self-Optimizing Mechatronic Systems with MechatronicUML. In Camara, J., de Lemos, R., Ghezzi, C., Lopes, A., eds.: *Assurances for Self-Adaptive Systems*. Volume 7740 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*. Springer (2013) 152–186
29. Giese, H., Burmester, S., Schäfer, W., Oberschelp, O.: Modular Design and Verification of Component-Based Mechatronic Systems with Online-Reconfiguration. In: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGSOFT Twelfth International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering. SIGSOFT '04/FSE-12, ACM* (2004) 179–188
30. Giese, H., Tichy, M., Burmester, S., Schäfer, W., Flake, S.: Towards the compositional verification of real-time uml designs. In: *Proceedings of the 9th European Software Engineering Conference Held Jointly with 11th ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering. ESEC/FSE-11, New York, NY, USA, ACM* (2003) 38–47

31. Becker, B., Beyer, D., Giese, H., Klein, F., Schilling, D.: Symbolic Invariant Verification for Systems with Dynamic Structural Adaptation. In: Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Software Engineering. ICSE '06, ACM (2006) 72–81
32. Giese, H., Klein, F.: Systematic verification of multi-agent systems based on rigorous executable specifications. *Int. J. Agent-Oriented Softw. Eng.* **1**(1) (2007) 28–62
33. Vogel, T., Giese, H.: Model-Driven Engineering of Self-Adaptive Software with EUREMA. *ACM Trans. Auton. Adapt. Syst.* **8**(4) (2014) 18:1–18:33
34. Rozenberg, G., ed.: *Handbook of Graph Grammars and Computing by Graph Transformation: Foundations*. World Scientific Pub Co (1997) Volume 1.
35. Rozenberg, G., Ehrig, H., Engels, G., Kreowski, H., eds.: *Handbook of graph grammars and computing by graph transformation: vol. 2: applications, languages, and tools*. World Scientific (1999)
36. : The Open Group Architectural Framework (TOGAF), version 9.1. Open Group Standard (2011)
37. Vassev, E., Hinchey, M.: The Challenge of Developing Autonomic Systems. *Computer* **43**(12) (2010) 93–96
38. Marconi, A., Bucchiarone, A., Bratanis, K., Brogi, A., Camara, J., Dranidis, D., Giese, H., Kazhamiakink, R., de Lemos, R., Marquezan, C., Metzger, A.: Research challenges on multi-layer and mixed-initiative monitoring and adaptation for service-based systems. In: *Software Services and Systems Research - Results and Challenges (S-Cube), 2012 Workshop on European*, IEEE (2012) 40–46
39. France, R., Rumpe, B.: Model-driven development of complex software: A research roadmap. In: *2007 Future of Software Engineering. FOSE '07*, Washington, DC, USA, IEEE Computer Society (2007) 37–54
40. Vogel, T., Giese, H.: Adaptation and Abstract Runtime Models. In: *Proceedings of the 2010 ICSE Workshop on Software Engineering for Adaptive and Self-Managing Systems. SEAMS '10*, ACM (2010) 39–48
41. Vogel, T., Seibel, A., Giese, H.: The Role of Models and Megamodels at Runtime. In Dingel, J., Solberg, A., eds.: *Models in Software Engineering*. Volume 6627 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*. Springer (2011) 224–238
42. Kephart, J.O., Chess, D.: The Vision of Autonomic Computing. *Computer* **36**(1) (2003) 41–50
43. Giese, H., Lambers, L., Becker, B., Hildebrandt, S., Neumann, S., Vogel, T., Wa'tzoldt, S.: Graph Transformations for MDE, Adaptation, and Models at Runtime. In Bernardo, M., Cortellessa, V., Pierantonio, A., eds.: *Formal Methods for Model-Driven Engineering*. Volume 7320 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*. Springer (2012) 137–191
44. Klein, F., Giese, H.: Joint Structural and Temporal Property Specification using Timed Story Sequence Diagrams. In Dwyer, M.B., Lopes, A., eds.: *Fundamental Approaches to Software Engineering*. Volume 4422 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*., Springer (2007) 185–199
45. Becker, B.: Architectural modelling and verification of open service-oriented systems of systems. PhD thesis, Hasso-Plattner-Institut fu'r Softwaresystemtechnik, Universita't Potsdam (2014)
46. Giese, H., Burmester, S., Klein, F., Schilling, D., Tichy, M.: Multi-Agent System Design for Safety-Critical Self-Optimizing Mechatronic Systems with UML. In Henderson-Sellers, B., Debenham, J., eds.: *OOPSLA 2003 - Second International Workshop on Agent-Oriented Methodologies*, Anaheim, CA, USA, Center for Object Technology Applications and Research (COTAR), University of Technology, Sydney, Australia (2003) 21–32
47. Becker, B., Giese, H.: Modeling of Correct Self-Adaptive Systems: A Graph Transformation System Based Approach. In: *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Soft*

- Computing As Transdisciplinary Science and Technology. CSTST '08, ACM (2008) 508–516
48. Giese, H., Hildebrandt, S., Lambers, L.: Bridging the gap between formal semantics and implementation of triple graph grammars. *Software and Systems Modeling* **13**(1) (2014) 273–299
 49. Becker, B., Giese, H.: On Safe Service-Oriented Real-Time Coordination for Autonomous Vehicles. In: Proc. of the 11th IEEE International Symposium on Object Oriented Real-Time Distributed Computing (ISORC), IEEE Computer Society Press (2008) 203–210
 50. Krause, C., Giese, H.: Probabilistic Graph Transformation Systems. In Ehrig, H., Engels, G., Kreowski, H.J., Rozenberg, G., eds.: Proceedings of Intl. Conf. on Graph Transformation (ICGT' 12). Volume 7562 of Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)., Springer (2012) 311–325
 51. Becker, B., Giese, H.: Cyber-Physical Systems with Dynamic Structure: Towards Modeling and Verification of Inductive Invariants. Technical Report 64, Hasso Plattner Institute at the University of Potsdam, Germany (2012)
 52. Giese, H., Becker, B.: Modeling and Verifying Dynamic Evolving Service-Oriented Architectures. Technical Report 75, Hasso Plattner Institute at the University of Potsdam, Germany (2013)
 53. Conant, R.C., Ashby, W.R.: Every good regulator of a system must be a model of that system. *Intl. J. Systems Science* **1**(2) (1970) 89–97
 54. Simon, H.A.: *The Sciences of the Artificial*. 3 edn. The MIT Press (1996) 57. Meyer, B.: 30. In: *Concurrency, distribution, client-server and the Internet*. 2 edn. Prentice Hall (1997) 951–1036
 58. Minsky, N.H., Ungureanu, V.: Law-governed interaction: a coordination and control mechanism for heterogeneous distributed systems. *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology (TOSEM)* **9**(3) (2000) 273–305